

Analysis of Logistics Course Test Anxiety Among University Students Studying Logistics

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Abstract

This study examined the cognitive and behavioral dimensions of test anxiety levels in logistics courses among university students studying logistics and evaluated the demographic factors influencing this anxiety. The study was conducted with undergraduate and associate degree students studying at Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University. A questionnaire was administered to determine students' test anxiety levels in the logistics course. The obtained data were analyzed using regression, independent t-tests, and ANOVA tests with the SPSS 22 software package, in accordance with the research questions and hypotheses. The results indicate that students' test anxiety is at a moderate-to-high level, and cognitive anxiety significantly affects behavioral anxiety. It was determined that gender, education level, and interest in the course did not significantly influence test anxiety. In addition, it was revealed that students' success in the logistics course enhanced their general academic self-confidence. This study is expected to expand academic knowledge by providing important findings for making logistics education more effective.

Lojistik Eğitimi Alan Üniversite Öğrencilerinin Lojistik Dersi Sınav Kaygılarının Analizi

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Lojistik Sektörü,
Lojistik Eğitimi,
Lojistik Sınav
Kaygısı, Bilişsel
Kaygı, Davranışsal
Kaygı

Özet

Bu çalışmada, lojistik dersi alan üniversite öğrencilerinin lojistik dersi sınav kaygı düzeyleri bilişsel ve davranışsal boyutlarıyla incelenmiş ve bu kaygıyı etkileyen demografik faktörler değerlendirilmiştir. Çalışma Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey Üniversitesinde eğitim gören lisans ve ön lisans öğrencileri ile gerçekleştirilmiştir. Öğrencilerin lojistik dersi sınav kaygısı düzeylerini tespit etmek için anket uygulanmıştır. Elde edilen veriler, araştırma soruları ve hipotezler doğrultusunda SPSS 22 paket programı ile regresyon, bağımsız t testi ve ANOVA testleri ile analiz edilmiştir. Sonuçlar, öğrencilerin sınav kaygılarının orta-yüksek düzeyde olduğunu göstermekte ve bilişsel kaygının davranışsal kaygı üzerinde anlamlı bir etkisi olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Cinsiyet, eğitim seviyesi ve derse duyulan ilginin sınav kaygısı üzerinde anlamlı bir farklılık oluşturmadığı tespit edilmiştir. Ayrıca, öğrencilerin lojistik dersinde elde ettikleri başarıların, genel akademik özgüvenlerini artırdığı ortaya konmuştur. Çalışmanın lojistik eğitiminin daha etkili hale getirilmesi için önemli bulgular sunarak akademik bilgi birikimini genişleteceği düşünülmektedir.

1. INTRODUCTION

The logistics sector has become an indispensable element of the economy today, in an era of accelerated globalization and technological advancements. The development of global trade leads to increased demand for logistics activities and expands business and investment opportunities (Gani, 2017). A large part of international trade is based on logistics operations, and effective logistics management has become a determining factor for companies to gain a competitive advantage. In Turkey, the logistics sector has recorded significant growth in recent years, and its contribution to the national economy has gradually increased. In particular, with its geographical location, transit routes, and developing economy, Turkey has the potential to become a regional logistics center (Erdoğan, 2019). However, in order for this growth to be sustainable, the logistics infrastructure requires strengthening, and modern technologies need to be integrated (Karagöz & Doyduk, 2020). Logistics operations play a pivotal role across all stages of the supply chain, and changing conditions in the global order directly affect the logistics sector (Mercimek & Geçkil, 2021). These developments increase the importance of conducting logistics activities effectively and efficiently, making logistics a sector with high potential in terms of providing employment (Kamacı, 2024). Companies encounter various challenges during this development process. A significant obstacle to this transformation is the lack of a trained workforce (Çopuroğlu et al., 2017). Since the sector requires highly coordinated efforts and operates in a mobile area with complex business processes, it needs a workforce with high analytical skills that can effectively manage processes and adapt to technological innovations (Dündar et al., 2024). Since this situation points out the value of training qualified personnel in the field of logistics, logistics education becomes a primary responsibility of the relevant departments of universities in this field (Şahin & Özkaya, 2020).

The fact that students studying at universities work in the relevant sector after graduation is considered a crucial resource for meeting the sector's workforce demand in the sector (Karasoy, 2022). Logistics education at universities aims to provide qualified individuals to the sector by combining theoretical knowledge with practical applications. Logistics courses may cause anxiety for some students as they require skills such as complex problem solving and analytical thinking. Test anxiety is a critical factor in this regard and negatively affects students' performance in exams and makes learning processes difficult (Gürpınar et al., 2019; Sarason, 1984). Test anxiety, often reported to be higher among university students compared to other educational levels, is a common problem among university students (Doğan, 2020). Elevated test anxiety may cause students to fail in logistics courses, decrease their motivation, and even decrease their interest in the logistics sector.

Students' anxiety can negatively affect their lives and may lead to the emergence of some behavioural disorders (Yenilmez & Akman, 2023). Determining the test anxiety levels of university students studying logistics and analysing the factors affecting this anxiety is important for both enhancing academic success and preparing better-equipped individuals for the sector. Measuring test anxiety enables the identification of students' anxiety levels and the development of strategies to reduce it. Managing test anxiety will positively affect students' educational processes and increase their success in this field. This study aims to analyse the test anxiety of university students studying logistics.

There have been extensive studies on test anxiety (Alpert & Haber, 1960; Çapulcuoğlu & Gündüz, 2013; Doğan, 2020; Gül, 2023; Hembree, 1988; Mandler & Sarason, 1952; Meichenbaum & Butler, 1980; Zuriff, 1997). However, no study analyzing test anxiety specifically among students studying logistics was found in the existing literature. This research will make a significant contribution to the literature by adopting an original approach that analyzes the cognitive and behavioral dimensions of test anxiety, focusing on a discipline like logistics, which is gaining increasing international importance and where technical and analytical competencies are crucial. The absence of studies in the literature that analyze students' test anxiety by focusing on logistics education further supports the originality of this study. It is anticipated that this study will expand academic knowledge by providing important findings to enhance the effectiveness of logistics education and contribute to the development of strategies for anxiety reduction in curricula.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Logistics Education

The logistics sector has emerged as one of the main factors contributing to a country's competitive advantage. The sector is growing every day and its importance is increasing. It is estimated that the market size of the sector at the global level will reach approximately 16 billion dollars in 2026 (Özoğlu et al., 2020). Given intensifying competition, the pursuit of high efficiency with minimal cost, customer satisfaction, new market

exploration, and evolving technologies, businesses are required to provide services with modern, scientifically-grounded, and trained personnel. For this reason, it is considered important to train professionals with specialized knowledge, social skills and analytical skills in the field of logistics to achieve sector targets and meet its evolving demands (Jian, 2011). The logistics industry has emerged as one of the most vital service sectors creating employment in recent years. Companies are increasingly seeking to recruit individuals trained in this field, leading to a growing demand for university programs specializing in logistics. Scientific approaches have revealed that logistics education is a necessary and indispensable development that cannot be postponed (Çıkmak, 2016).

Logistics is one of the basic disciplines that enable the effective management of global supply chains. Today, the increasing complexity of logistics processes and the prominence of concepts such as digital transformation and sustainability have highlighted the growing importance of logistics training. Logistics training can be defined as a complex training encompassing financial and contractual elements, equipment and technology features, as well as organizational planning methods (Naim et al., 2000). While logistics education was first offered in the United States of America in 1975, in Turkey, it was first provided as a higher education program in 1999. In the following years, with the rapid development of the sector, logistics and supply chain management departments were established in many universities both in Turkey and in the world (Karasoy, 2022). While logistics staff working in the field are mostly trained by vocational colleges, planners, managers, or practitioners are educated by four-year colleges and faculties (Çalışkan & Öztürkoğlu, 2014).

Logistics education is structured around two main models: business and engineering. In the engineering model, education is supported by business courses, which are especially useful for management, and the emphasis is on supply chain management and logistics courses along with engineering courses. In the business model, on the other hand, education focuses on logistics and supply chain management courses as well as economics courses, and education is supported by engineering courses that aid in decision-making and system analysis (Hayward & Omurtag, 2003).

Logistics is one of the leading sectors in terms of its impact on economic activity and employment potential. The demands placed on universities to train individuals specialised in logistics are increasing day by day. Recognizing logistics education as a significant need, academic discussions have emerged concerning its current state, challenges, and proposed solutions. The literature primarily focuses on assessing the status of logistics education (Bali et al., 2016; Çalışkan & Öztürkoğlu, 2014; Çıkmak, 2016; Gravier & Theodore Farris, 2008; Jian, 2011; Kamacı, 2023; Lutz & Birou, 2013; Özoğlu et al., 2020) and the sector's expectations from university-level logistics education (Cekerol, 2020; Hocoğlu et al., 2015; Li & Jia, 2024; Sayın & Küçük, 2020; Van Hoek, 2001).

The innovative structure and dynamic development of logistics education are evaluated in five interconnected stages. It has been found that the expectations of the labour market and student feedback are the key determinants for achieving the goals of logistics higher education and fulfilling labor market demands. While professional competencies and technical expertise are considered important at management levels, it has been revealed that soft skills are also prioritized (Jian, 2011).

The logistics sector is distinguished from other sectors by its dual technology-intensive and labor-intensive structure and is considered to be among the sectors of most strategic importance for economies. The sector has a horizontal effect that directly affects the competitiveness of almost all sectors, from production to trade, through the employment it generates. The increasing importance of logistics in the international arena highlights the growing importance of human resources in this sector. It has become a necessity for logistics sector employees to have the professional competence, knowledge, and skills required in the contemporary era. In order to meet the needs of the sector, higher education institutions are also constantly working towards ensuring a sufficient number of qualified personnel. However, it is also important that most of these features employees should possess are acquired during their university education. Highly motivated students who increase their professional knowledge and skills through their academic training and hands-on experience gained from on-the-job training will be more easily employed in the field of logistics as a skilled workforce. The employment of qualified personnel within the sector's enterprises will positively affect both the economic and commercial development of the countries and elevate the logistics sector to a competitive level (Özkan & Bozyiğit, 2020).

2.2. Test Anxiety

Test anxiety is described as a distressing emotional condition with both physiological and behavioral components, which typically arises in evaluative situations or, more specifically, in formal examinations, preventing individuals from demonstrating their actual performance (Auerbach & Spielberger, 1972; Gibson, 2014). Test anxiety is also conceptualized as a set of behaviors that impact academic performance, encompassing inadequate study skills, excessive physiological reactions, and task-irrelevant mental activities (Kirkland & Hollandsworth, 1980). The Motivational Drive Model, developed by Mandler and Sarason (1952), is among the pioneering studies that explore the relationship between anxiety and learning. This model represents the first approach that distinguishes test anxiety from the broader concept of general anxiety. In their research, they assessed the impact of anxiety on the learning process and demonstrated how test anxiety can influence an individual's performance. Alpert and Haber (1960) categorized test anxiety into facilitative (mild anxiety) and debilitating (characterized by negative thoughts). This distinction shows that anxiety does not always have a negative effect and that a certain level of anxiety can improve performance. In Mandler and Sarason's theory of test anxiety, it is argued that individuals exhibit two types of responses: subject-oriented and non-subject-oriented. The main problems of students with test anxiety arise from non-subject-oriented reactions, and it is stated that students with such reactions exhibit responses that impair test performance (Behti, 2015; Mandler & Sarason, 1952).

The complexity of anxiety, which encompasses worry, obsession, sadness, destructive emotions, and maladaptive behaviours, has posed a challenge for researchers in distinguishing between these components. In light of this, Liebert & Morris (1967) conducted research to explain the nature of test anxiety and pioneered theoretical developments. As a result of their research, they stated that anxiety has two dimensions: cognitive (worry) and affective (emotional) dimensions. The cognitive aspect of test anxiety comprises test anxiety and includes thoughts such as insecurity, social comparison, apprehension about failure consequences, and negative self-evaluation. The affective dimension, conversely, includes behavioral reactions such as nervousness, dry mouth, stomach pain, panic, accelerated heartbeat, restlessness, and trembling (Ataş, 2021; Salamé, 1984). While anxiety perceives the exam as a threat and focuses on past and future risks, affective anxiety is considered more momentary (Kaplan et al., 1979).

Meichenbaum and Butler (1980) explained exam anxiety with four variables. These variables include internal dialogue, characterized by negative self-talk; behavioral actions, encompassing observed behaviors, study habits, and test-solving ability; behavioral outcomes, referring to achieved test results, grades, or feedback; and cognitive structure, representing the student's motivation or orientation for their behavior. Sarason (1984) categorized test anxiety cognitively as task-related and task-irrelevant. He stated that the low performance of individuals with high levels of anxiety is mostly due to differences in attentional focus. He also suggested that a person's level of test anxiety is, to a significant extent, a product of experiences that affect attention. A person with high test anxiety tends to exhibit self-focused, inhibitory reactions when faced with evaluative conditions. Hembree (1988) suggested that the failure of students who experience test anxiety and perform poorly can be attributed to limited abilities and ineffective study techniques.

Test anxiety has also been conceptualized as state and trait anxiety, but it has been suggested that test anxiety is generally a situational anxiety. While state anxiety refers to the current level of anxiety in a particular situation, trait anxiety is more related to the personality characteristics of the individual and reflects an individual's general predisposition to experience anxiety (Spielberger & Vagg, 1995). In this context, test anxiety can have both situational and personal characteristics. Students with high test anxiety may perceive exams as more threatening and tend to exhibit higher levels of state anxiety (Gibson, 2014). Unlike Liebert and Morris, Zuriff (1997) stated that test anxiety has a three-component structure. These include subjective distress, manifesting as fear, anxiety, and tension; physical symptoms like trembling and sweating; and cognitive effects such as difficulties in focusing.

Studies in the literature have demonstrated that high test anxiety negatively affects the learning process, academic achievement, motivation, and self-efficacy (Ergene, 2003; Wu & Chang, 2021). However, when exposed to a test situation, individuals with test anxiety may exhibit all, some, or none of these anxiety responses. This specific reaction can differ based on the individual's inherent traits, prior experiences, the complexity of the task, and various situational factors influencing anxiety levels (Zeidner, 2007).

Although the cognitive and affective components of test anxiety are related to each other, they are empirically different. It has been considered particularly beneficial by researchers to separate test anxiety into cognitive

(worry) aspects and behavioural (emotional) aspects. Therefore, individuals experiencing test anxiety can be characterized by their thoughts, physiological reactions, emotions, and observable behaviors typically exhibited during the assessment process (Salamé, 1984).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to analyse the cognitive and behavioural aspects of logistics course-specific test anxiety of university students enrolled in logistics programs within the established theoretical framework of test anxiety. Test anxiety theory explains how individuals develop mental preparation and behavioral responses to test situations. In the theoretical and practical applications of logistics education, being aware of and managing students' test anxiety will contribute to more efficient teaching processes.

In this context, this study will seek answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of test anxiety of students studying logistics?
2. Is there a significant relationship between cognitive and behavioural dimensions of logistics course test anxiety?
3. Do demographic variables have a significant effect on test anxiety?

3.2. Sampling and Data Collection

The study employed convenience sampling, one of the non-probability sampling techniques. Convenience sampling is a technique in which data is collected from the most easily accessible subjects by utilising easily accessible means. It is frequently preferred in social science research, especially since it is not always possible to reach a larger population due to factors such as time, budget, and resource limitations (Creswell & Creswell, 2017; Gürbüz & Şahin, 2018). The sample of the study consisted of students enrolled in associate and undergraduate programs providing logistics education at Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University. The questionnaire, designed in accordance with the research purpose, was administered face-to-face to a total of N = 250 students (152 undergraduate and 98 associate degree students) enrolled in the logistics course during the spring and autumn semesters of 2024; students who could not be reached directly were contacted online. At the beginning of the questionnaire form, the purpose of the research was explained to the participants, and then participants were informed that their participation was voluntary, they could withdraw at any time, and the collected data would be used solely for the study's collective analysis. Approximately an 84% response rate was achieved, and data were obtained from a total of 212 students. Incomplete or blank questionnaires were removed, and a total of n = 210 valid responses were included in the study.

This is a quantitative study investigating the presence or absence of relationships. A questionnaire was employed as one of the data collection methods in the research. The questionnaire form consists of two parts: questions about demographic characteristics and statements designed to measure logistics course test anxiety. For the test anxiety scale used in the questionnaire, the statements were adapted from the study by Gül (2023) to be suitable for students in logistics courses. The scale's total internal consistency (reliability) coefficient was reported as .78, and responses were collected on a 5-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Disagree, 5=Strongly Agree). Consistent with the study's objective, the test anxiety scale in the questionnaire form was evaluated by three (3) field experts, both individually and collectively, based on the cognitive and behavioral elements specified by Liebert & Morris (1967) and Salamé (1984). As a result of the evaluation, 13 statements of the scale were divided into 2 dimensions as cognitive (worry-anxiety) and behavioural (physiological reactions).

3.3. Analysing the Data

To determine the construct validity of the scale, factor analysis was conducted using principal components and direct oblique rotation (direct oblimin) methods. As a result of the analysis, since factor loadings of 0.40 and above are accepted as ideal (Field, 2009), items below 0.40 and overlapping items were removed, and the analysis continued with 10 items, 7 of which were cognitive and 3 of which were behavioural. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy value was determined to be 0.869. This value indicates that the sample size is sufficient for the analysis ($0.869 > 0.50$). In addition, sampling adequacy was confirmed by determining that the KMO values of each item were above 0.50 (Field, 2009). Bartlett's Test of Sphericity yielded a result of $\chi^2(55)=674.336, p<.05$, further revealing that the correlation between the items was of sufficient magnitude. As a result of the factor analysis, it was determined that the scale comprised a two-sub-dimension structure,

explaining 51.53% of the total variance, thus confirming the two-factor structure. As a result of the reliability test of the scale, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was found to be $\alpha=0.824$. In addition, the reliability of the cognitive dimension was $\alpha=0.716$ and the reliability of the behavioural dimension was $\alpha=0.740$. Since a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.70 and above is considered sufficient for the reliability of the scale (Gürbüz & Şahin, 2018), the scale, along with its sub-dimensions, was deemed a reliable measurement tool. The normality of the data distribution was measured using Skewness and Kurtosis coefficients. It was determined that these values were between -1.5 and +1.5 (0.517 and 0.497), and this range indicated the normal distribution value (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). Since the data showed normal distribution, parametric tests were used in the analysis.

Descriptive statistics of the research data are shown in the table below.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics on Demographic Characteristics

Gender	n	%
Male	116	55.2
Female	94	44.8
Educational Programme	n	%
Undergraduate	119	56.7
Associate's degree	91	43.3
Interest in the Course	n	%
I like it very much	31	14.8
I like	115	54.8
Neither like nor dislike	54	25.7
I don't like	8	3.8
I don't like it at all	2	1.0
Reason for Lack of Interest/Interest in the Course	n	%
Logistics itself	123	58.6
Course instructor	41	19.5
The way the course is lectured	29	13.8
Course exams	9	4.3
Others	8	3.8

According to the descriptive information in Table 1, the majority of the students participating in the study are male and undergraduate students. Approximately 70% of the students stated that they liked the logistics course, and 58.6% of them stated that the reason for their interest or lack of interest was the logistics itself.

3.4. Hypotheses of the Study

While cognitive test anxiety includes the student's negative cognitions rooted in the fear of failure during the exam process, behavioural (affective) test anxiety is related to the manifestation through physical reactions (Sarason & Sarason, 1987). Studies reveal that cognitive anxiety is related to behavioural anxiety and can directly affect performance during the exam by eliciting behavioural reactions (Putwain & Daly, 2013; Schwarzer, 1980).

H1: Students' logistics course cognitive test anxiety has a meaningful effect on their behavioural test anxiety.

In the literature, it has been revealed that demographic components characterised as individual factors influence anxiety levels. Studies generally show that test anxiety differs according to gender, and women report higher test anxiety than men (Cassady & Johnson, 2002; Oral Kara, Akın & Alp, 2020; Yıldız, 2021).

H2: Students' logistics course test anxiety shows a meaningful difference according to gender.

It is posited that students' academic anxiety levels may vary depending on their educational program (Doğan, 2020; Putwain & Daly, 2013; Schunk & Pajares, 2002). Therefore, academic expectations in associate degree and undergraduate programs may affect students' test anxiety at different levels.

H3: Students' logistics course test anxiety shows a meaningful difference according to the program of study.

It is stated that the effect of interest in the course on test anxiety is directly related to students' self-efficacy perceptions and academic motivation during the exam process (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002). Furthermore, increased interest in the exam is identified as a predictor of test anxiety (Erel, 2022; Torrano et al., 2020).

H4: Students' logistics test anxiety shows a meaningful difference according to their interest in the logistics course.

4. FINDINGS

The results of the descriptive analyses conducted to reveal the test anxiety levels of the students enrolled in logistics courses are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Test Anxiety Scale

Items	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Cognitive – 1	210	3.924	1.0998
Cognitive – 2	210	2.133	1.1866
Cognitive – 3	210	3.314	1.4264
Cognitive – 4	210	3.624	1.2816
Cognitive – 5	210	3.457	1.1822
Cognitive – 6	210	3.652	1.1608
Cognitive – 7	210	3.381	1.1971
Behavioural – 1	210	3.348	1.3477
Behavioural – 2	210	3.586	1.2735
Behavioural – 3	210	3.181	1.3254
Test Anxiety (General)	210	3.333	0.7550

According to the results obtained, the statement with the highest mean in the test anxiety scale was the first item (Cognitive-1) in the cognitive dimension, namely, “Being successful in the logistics course exams causes my self-confidence to increase in other exams.” The statement with the lowest mean was the second item in the cognitive dimension (Cognitive-2), ‘I hate it when the lecturer asks questions about logistics in the course.’ The overall mean of the students' answers to the test anxiety scale is 3.333. According to this, it can be said that the students' level of test anxiety in the logistics course generally has a moderate-to-high average level.

Simple regression analysis was performed to examine the effect of students' cognitive test anxiety on their behavioural test anxiety in the logistics course.

Table 3. Analysis of the Effect of Students' Cognitive Test Anxiety on Behavioural Test Anxiety in Logistics Course

Dependent Variable: Behavioural Test Anxiety	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.(p)
(Constant)	1.115	0.162		6.886	0.000
Cognitive Test Anxiety	0.591	0.046	0.667	12.927	0.000

n=210, R=0.667, R²= 0.445, p<0.05

An examination of the results presented in Table 3 reveals a statistically significant positive relationship between students' cognitive test anxiety and their behavioural test anxiety in the logistics course ($R=0.667$, $p=0.000$). In this case, it can be said that when students' cognitive test anxiety increases, their behavioural anxiety will also increase. Furthermore, examining the significance of the regression coefficient reveals that students' cognitive test anxiety in the logistics course significantly affects their behavioral test anxiety ($\beta=0.667$). According to the coefficient of determination, 44.5% of the variance in behavioral anxiety is explained by cognitive anxiety ($R^2=0.445$). According to the results of the analyses, hypothesis H1 was supported.

Independent samples t-test analysis was performed to test whether the students' logistics course test anxiety differed according to their gender.

Table 4. Difference Test of Students' Logistics Course Test Anxiety According to Gender

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig. (p)
Test Anxiety	Male	116	3.2939	0.83003	0.390
	Female	94	3.3820	0.65183	

According to the results of the analyses in Table 4, students' logistics course test anxiety does not show a statistically meaningful difference according to gender ($p=0.390$). According to the results of the analysis, the H2 hypothesis is not supported.

Independent samples t-test analysis was performed to test whether the students' logistics course test anxiety differs according to their education program.

Table 5. Difference Test of Students' Logistics Course Test Anxiety According to Education Program

	Educational Program	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig. (p)
Test Anxiety	Undergraduate	119	3.3170	0.79092	0.718
	Associate Degree	91	3.3546	0.70912	

According to the results of the analysis in Table 5, students' logistics course test anxiety does not show a meaningful difference according to their education programme ($p=0.718$). According to the results of the analysis, hypothesis H3 is not supported.

Independent samples one-way an ANOVA test was conducted to test whether the logistics course test anxiety of the students enrolled in logistics courses differed according to their interest in the course.

Table 6. Difference Test of Students' Logistics Course Test Anxiety According to Their Interest in the Course

	Interest in the Course	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig. (p)
Test Anxiety	I like it very much	31	3.3226	0.86494	0.238
	I like	115	3.3004	0.75180	
	Neither like nor dislike	54	3.3704	0.68210	
	I don't like	8	3.2955	0.76021	
	I don't like it at all	2	4.5455	0.64282	

As a result of the analysis, Levene's test indicated that the variances were homogeneously distributed ($p=0.604$, $p>0.05$) and ANOVA results were examined. According to the results in Table 6, students' logistics course test anxiety does not show a meaningful difference according to their interest in the course ($p=0.238$). In this case, hypothesis H4 was not supported.

The general view of the hypothesis results is given in Table 7.

Table 7. Hypothesis Test Results

	Hypothesis	Conclusion
H1	Students' logistics course cognitive test anxiety has a meaningful effect on their behavioural test anxiety.	Supported
H2	Students' logistics course test anxiety shows a meaningful difference according to gender.	Not Supported
H3	Students' logistics course test anxiety shows a meaningful difference according to the programme of study.	Not Supported
H4	Students' logistics test anxiety shows a meaningful difference according to their interest in the logistics course.	Not Supported

5. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In this study, the test anxiety levels of university students studying logistics were examined in the context of demographic variables such as gender, education programme and interest in the course, as well as cognitive and behavioural dimensions. Hypotheses were tested with the findings obtained, and the results were evaluated in the context of the relevant literature.

From the research findings, it was observed that students' logistics course test anxiety had a moderate-to-high average level. This finding shows that students have considerable anxiety about the logistics course exams, although it is not very high. In particular, the mean of the statement 'Being successful in logistics course exams will increase my confidence in other exams' was observed as 3,924. Accordingly, it can be said that students believe that their success in the logistics course increases their general academic self-confidence. This is consistent with the findings that success experiences positively affect students' self-efficacy perception (Bandura, 1997; Schunk & Pajares, 2002). In addition, it can be said that logistics course exams are perceived by students as a psychological asset that not only measures their performance in the course but also influences their success in other examinations. On the other hand, the mean of the statement 'I hate it when the lecturer asks questions about logistics in the course' was determined as 2.133. This low mean indicates that students' negative feelings about in-class interaction and discussion environment are relatively lower, suggesting that their perceptions of active classroom discussion and question-and-answer sessions evoke less anxiety. This suggests that students' test anxiety is more focused on exam performance and results, while classroom interaction is perceived as less threatening. In general, the mean of the test anxiety scale reveals that test anxiety is an important variable in the context of the logistics course. Studies have shown that students with low test anxiety and high academic motivation tend to have high self-efficacy and academic performance (Ergene, 2003; Wu & Chang, 2021; Yurt, 2022). The findings also point to the need to examine the potential effects of cognitive and behavioural dimensions of test anxiety on students' academic motivation, performance, and self-efficacy in more depth.

According to the results of regression analysis, it was found that cognitive test anxiety had a significant positive effect on the behavioural anxiety of university students studying logistics. This finding shows that students' cognitions (cognitive anxiety) experienced before and during the exam may trigger physical reactions (behavioral anxiety) during the exam process. This result is consistent with the findings that test anxiety is a multidimensional structure and that cognitive processes directly affect students' behaviours during the exam (Sarason, 1984). Specific to the logistics course, it is understood that when students experience test anxiety, this anxiety does not only remain at a purely cognitive level, but also manifests in behavioral reactions that can affect their test performance. Considering that self-confidence and test anxiety have a negative relationship (Gül, 2023), logistics education, as a field where analytical thinking and problem-solving skills are critical, may increase cognitive test anxiety and behavioural reactions impacting test performance in students who lack self-confidence. This situation indicates that the development of intervention programs for the cognitive component of test anxiety will be important for both logistics education and employability within the sector.

The fact that the logistics course test anxiety levels of university students studying logistics do not differ according to gender also suggests that gender does not have a determining effect on test anxiety among students studying logistics. Although there are findings in the literature that female students generally experience higher test anxiety (Çapulcuoğlu & Gündüz, 2013; Cassady & Johnson, 2002; Putwain & Daly, 2013), there are also studies indicating higher anxiety levels in male students compared to female students (Núñez et al., 2020). However, it can be said that the fact that students share similar motivation and career expectations in technical and practice-based fields such as logistics may contribute to minimizing gender-related anxiety differences.

In the comparisons made between undergraduate and associate degree students, no significant difference was found in the test anxiety levels of the students in the logistics course. In the literature, it is generally stated that there may be differences in students' test anxiety depending on the academic level (Hembree, 1988). However, in this study, it was observed that undergraduate and associate degree students have similar levels of test anxiety. With this result, it can be said that logistics education has similar evaluation criteria at both undergraduate and associate degree levels. Thus, it is understood that the education program does not indicate test anxiety levels as a determining factor and that individual factors and expectations are primarily influential in logistics education.

The findings showed that there was no significant difference in the level of test anxiety of university students according to their interest in the logistics course. In the questionnaire, it was observed that approximately 69.6% of the students had a positive attitude towards the logistics course; 14.8% of them responded as 'I like it very much' and 54.8% as 'I like it'. In addition, the main reason for the students' interest in the course was logistics itself. This situation reveals that although the interest in the logistics course is high, test anxiety is not directly related to this level of interest. In other words, interest in the logistics course alone may not be sufficient to reduce students' test anxiety; it can be said that test anxiety is shaped by factors such as academic evaluation processes, exam format, and personal factors (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002; Pekrun et al., 2002). This situation

points to the importance of developing not only interest in the course but also effective test anxiety management skills in order to be successful in logistics courses.

The logistics sector is in great need of qualified human resources due to globalised supply chains, digital transformation, and continuous competition. In this context, test anxiety of students studying logistics can have direct effects on academic performance and professional competence. The findings of the study reveal that cognitive test anxiety has a significant effect on behavioural anxiety and emphasise the necessity of developing anxiety management strategies in education programs. The results obtained in the logistics course also provide important contributions by revealing the field-specific determinants of students' test anxiety within this course.

In future studies, in order to examine the effects of test anxiety on logistics education and employment in the sector more comprehensively, it is recommended to conduct comparative analyses with data to be obtained from different universities and programmes. In addition, implementing intervention programs to reduce test anxiety and examining the long-term effects of these interventions on academic performance and professional life will make significant contributions to both the academic literature and the human resources strategies of the logistics sector.

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